

Thermal Decomposition of Photosensitive Diazo Crown Ether Complexation^ψ

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The thermal decomposition of diazonium salts in solid and diazonium compounds complex with 18-crown-6 ether (CED) was studied by uv spectroscopy and thermogravimetric analysis. The fluorobenzene, phenol and BF₃ were detected from the thermal decomposition products of benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate (BD) in isopropyl alcohol (IPA) and dioxane by uv spectrophotometry. The mechanism of decomposition in IPA and dioxane is similar to the ionic mechanism reported in water. The rate of thermal decomposition in solid was larger than that in liquid. As the molar ratio of 18-crown-6 increased, the degradation temperature (*T_d*) of CED derived from BD was raised. When 18-crown-6 existed in excess, BD was easy to degrade because of hygroscopic property of 18-crown-6.

Photosensitive diazo compounds are utilised to the diazo type process¹, uv-fixable thermal recording^{2–4}, resist process^{5–7}, CEL (contrast enhancement lithography) materials⁸, phototackifiable film⁹, etc. When photosensitive diazo compounds are applied to the imaging process, they have the following merits: high resolution, short access time and so on, but the thermal stability is to be improved. There are many attempts to improve the stability, for example, the uv-fixable thermal recording material by the use of the encapsulated diazo compounds^{2–4}, and the photopolymer system based on the catalytic selectivity due to the coordination of the donor to the acceptor initiator below the critical temperature^{10,11}. It was demonstrated first by Gokel and Cram¹² and subsequently by Haymore *et al.*¹³ that 18-crown-6 complexed benzene diazonium cation in solution with the insertion of the diazonium moiety into the ligand cavity develop the diazo stability. Bartsch *et al.* found that the thermal decomposition rates in organic solvents¹⁴ and the photodecomposition in the solid phase¹⁵ were significantly reduced by the addition of crown ethers.

In this paper, the thermal decompositions of the solid diazo compound and diazo crown ether complex are studied. Many reports of thermal decomposition of diazonium salts in solution, such as aqueous solution (low pH)¹⁶, methyl alcohol^{17,18} etc. were reported by DeTar *et al.* The thermal decomposition in aqueous solution (pH 1–7)¹⁹ and aprotic polar solvent^{20,21} were reported too. But there are few reports of solid diazonium salts. It is important to study the solid diazo compounds because of the utilisation for imaging process. In order to improve the thermal decomposition of diazo compounds, the diazo compounds complex with crown ether were studied.

Results and Discussion

Thermal decomposition reaction of solid diazo compound :

Reaction products : Benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate (BD) (0.0096 g, 5×10^{-5} mol) dispersed in isopropyl alcohol (IPA) or dioxane were thermally decomposed. While heating, little bubbles were gen-

^ψPartly based on a presentation given at the Annual Meeting of the Society of Photographic Science and Technology th^l Japan (SPSTJ), Tokyo, Japan, 1991.

Fig 1 Thermal decomposition products in isopropyl alcohol (IPA) (benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate (BD) = 5.6×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) (1) 30°, (2) 40°, (3) 50° and (4) 60°

Fig 2 Thermal decomposition products in dioxane (benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate (BD) = 5.6×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) (1) 30°, (2) 40°, (3) 50° and (4) 60°

TABLE 1—MOLAR RATIO OF THERMAL DECOMPOSITIONS PRODUCTS OF BENZENE DIAZONIUM TETRAFLUOROBORATE (BD) IN IPA AND DIOXANE AT 60°

Decomposition products	Solvent	
	IPA	Dioxane
Fluorobenzene	0.28	0.56
Phenol	0.56	0.42
BF ₃	0.73	0.85

erated from the surface of powders and BD gradually dissolved into IPA. After complete dissolution of BD powder, an aliquot of the IPA solution was taken and analysed by uv spectrophotometry.

Uv spectra of decomposition products in IPA and dioxane are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The absorption bands at 250–268, 270–278 and 300–380 nm are assigned to fluorobenzene, phenol and *p*-hydroxyazobenzene. The decomposition products in IPA or dioxane are shown in Table 1. *p*-Hydroxyazobenzene was much produced at low temperature in IPA. It is considered BD resolved in IPA and was coupled with the decomposition products phenol for long time at low temperature. Decomposition products, BF₃, could not be detected directly because of overlapping of the characteristic band with those of other products. So BF₃ was determined indirectly from spectral change by coordination to lone-pair electrons of dimethylamino compounds²². 73% and 85% of BF₃ generated from

BD at 60° were detected in IPA and in dioxane, respectively. BD in IPA is dissociated into diazocation and BF₄, and the BF₃ generated by thermal decomposition of the residual BD is hydrolysed to give boron fluorohydroxide.

The decomposition products were mainly the fluorobenzene. This indicates that the mechanism of decomposition in IPA and dioxane is similar to the ionic mechanism²³ reported for decomposition in water¹⁶ and aprotic solvent^{20,21}.

Decomposition rate : The rates of thermal decomposition reaction of solvents were found to be of the first order. The rate constant and activation energy data are shown in Table 2. The rate constant in solvent is larger than that of solid BD and activation energy in solvent is smaller than that of solid BD.

TABLE 2—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT AND ACTIVATION FOR THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF BENZENE DIAZONIUM TETRAFLUOROBORATE (BD) IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Solvent	Dioxane	IPA ^a	CH ₃ CN ^b	H ₂ O ^c
<i>K</i> (s ⁻¹) (50°)	7.4×10^{-5}	4.9×10^{-4}	6.9×10^{-4} (45°)	7.7×10^{-4}
<i>E</i> (kcal mol ⁻¹)	20.8	20.4	29.7	18.2 (pH 7) 27.1 (low pH) ^d
	2.24	16.24	31.20	8.0

^aIsopropyl alcohol ^bRef 20 ^cRef 19 ^dRef 16

Thermal decomposition of diazo compound complex with crown ether :

In order to improve the thermal decomposition of diazo compounds, the diazo compounds with crown ether were studied. The stability of the diazo complex with crown ether (CED) is dependent on the size of diazonium cation relative to that of the hole of crown ether. The diameter of 15-crown-5, 18-crown-6, and 21-crown-7 are 1.7–2.2, 2.6–3.2 and 3.4–4.5 Å respectively. 18-Crown-6 is of appropriate size for diazonium cation (2.4 Å) and the 18-crown-6 complexed benzene diazonium cation (CED) has good stability²³. Hence 18-crown-6 was used in this report. Thermal decomposition of benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate with 18-crown-6 in 1,2-dichloroethane was reported by Kuokkanen and Virtanen²⁶. The thermal decomposition of benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate with 18-crown-6 was studied by thermogravimetric analysis. The relation of degradation temperature (T_d) and the composition of BD and 18-crown-6 is shown in Fig. 3 As

Fig 3 Effects of composition (18-crown-6 BD) on degradation temperature (T_d). BD = 5 mg (2.6×10^{-5} mol), 18-crown-6 = 1.4–10.9 mg (5×10^{-6} – 4.1×10^{-5} mol)

the molar ratio of 18-crown-6 increased, T_d of

CED increased and it became constant when the molar ratio of BD to 18-crown-6 equalled 1 : 1. The T_d of 1 : 1 (CED) was 17° higher than that of BD²⁷. It is considered that BD is coordinated by 18-crown-6 at ratio 1 : 1 (CED). The sample of CED was kept at 20°.

The relation of composition and remaining weight % of BD is shown in Fig. 4. As the molar ratio

Fig 4 Effects of composition (18-crown-6 BD) on remaining of weight % of benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate (BD) after 3 months in room temperature. BD = 1mg (5.2×10^{-5} mol), 18-crown-6 = 2.6–23.4 mg (5.2×10^{-6} – 1.4×10^{-4} mol)

of 18-crown-6 increased, the remaining weight % of BD increased. When 18-crown-6 existed in excess (more than 1 : 1), the remaining weight % decreased. It is because 18-crown-6 has hygroscopic property and BD is easy to decompose in water solution.

Conclusion :

The thermal decomposition of benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate (BD) was investigated in IPA and dioxane by uv spectrophotometry. The decomposition products were mainly the fluorobenzene. This indicates that the mechanism of decomposition in IPA and dioxane is similar to the ionic mechanism reported

for decomposition in water and aprotic polar solvents. BD complex with 18-crown-6 (CED) was studied by thermogravimetric analysis. CED (BD : 18-crown-6 = 1 : 1) was the most thermally stable complex. As the molar ratio of 18-crown-6 increased, the degradation temperature (T_d) of CED derived from BD was raised. When 18-crown-6 existed in excess BD was easy to degrade because of the hygroscopic nature of 18-crown-6.

Experimental

Benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate was obtained by adding aqueous hydrogen tetrafluoroborate to an aqueous solution of benzene diazonium chloride prepared from aniline. The crude crystalline solid was recrystallised from methanol. The other materials used were of extra pure grade.

Absorption spectra were measured with a Shimadzu UV-180 spectrophotometer equipped with coolants thermobath. The thermal analyses were performed by a Mac Science 001 thermal analyzer system at a heating rate of 5^o/min, for TGA and DTA under N₂ atmosphere.

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